

Electronic Patient Records for Dental School Clinics: More Than Paperless Systems

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Abstract: The Electronic Patient Record (EPR) or “computer-based medical record” is defined by the Patient Record Institute as “a repository for patient information with one health-care enterprise that is supported by digital computer input and integrated with other information sources.” The information technology revolution coupled with everyday use of computers in clinical dentistry has created new demand for electronic patient records. Ultimately, the EPR should improve health care quality. The major short-term disadvantage is cost, including software, equipment, training, and personnel time involved in the associated business process re-engineering. An internal review committee with expertise in information technology and/or database management evaluated commercially available software in light of the unique needs of academic dental facilities. This paper discusses their deficiencies and suggests areas for improvement. The dental profession should develop a more common record with standard diagnostic codes and clinical outcome measures to make the EPR more useful for clinical research and improve the quality of care.

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Key words: dental informatics, electronic patient records, dentistry

Submitted for publication 9/24/01; accepted 1/28/02

The Electronic Patient Record (EPR) or “computer-based medical record” is defined by the Patient Record Institute as “a repository for patient information with one health-care enterprise that is supported by digital computer input and integrated with other information sources.” The information technology revolution coupled with everyday use of computers in clinical dentistry has created new demand for electronic patient records. The benefits, particularly for large clinical institutions, are obvious: improved record control, easier document storage and access, better information for clinic management, and excellent data for evaluation of overall patient care. Ultimately, the EPR should improve health care quality.¹ The major short-term disadvantage is cost, including software, equipment, training, and personnel time involved in the associated business process re-engineering. A recent estimate from the Council on Competitiveness is that the full cost of implementing a fully integrated health information system is 7.5 to 13.5 percent of a clinic’s annual budgeted revenues.² That percentage may be higher for a typical dental school clinic in which true operating costs grossly exceed yearly revenues.

The EPR has many uses, including:

- *Quality indicators*—EPRs, if designed appropriately, can capture and allow the comparative analysis of patients or groups of providers for quality assurance functions.
- *Clinic patient population medical and dental history profiles*—Standardized coding and classification systems exist for medical diagnoses, and these include some dental codes. A more extensive diagnostic coding system, SNODENT, is under development by the American Dental Association for dental diagnoses. If medical and dental histories are recorded using diagnostic codes and stored appropriately, data can be extracted easily for dental school needs. Postgraduate programs needing patient information for accreditation purposes can determine the numbers of patients treated by residents with certain dental or medical diagnoses. This type of demographic data also is valuable to dental school faculty preparing grant applications for clinical studies.
- *Information support for clinical decision-making.* Several EPRs developed for specialty medical clinics provide treatment suggestions based on the patient’s signs and symptoms. This type of system in a dental school can be used to advise students

and faculty of evidence-based clinical practice guidelines for various clinical situations, including prescription advice. Several recent studies found that computer-based reminders increased compliance with practice guidelines for medicine.³⁻⁵

- *Decision support information for management of administrative functions*, such as activity-based costing, productivity reporting, patient recall, and patient education.
- *Electronic data interchange*, including teledentistry, data sharing with other health professionals, and third-party payors.

Abbreviated History of Electronic Patient Records in Medicine

One of the biggest challenges for developers of electronic medical records is the integration of narratives (all qualitative and semi-quantitative data gathered by physicians). Ideally, the EPR should integrate descriptive clinical notes, dictated summaries, letters to referring professionals, progress and procedure notes (including operative notes), and supporting reports from pathology and clinical laboratories. This process is much more complicated when the data is narrative text rather than categorized as a data element.

The development of the EPR started in the late 1960s.^{6,7} Early systems such as the Problem-Oriented Medical Information System (PROMIS) from the Medical Center Hospital of Vermont structured the record according to a patient problem list using a SOAP (subjective, objective, assessment, plan) format.⁷ The system guided physicians through a structured eight-step format, which users complained was dogmatic. This problem ultimately led to the demise of the system.

Soon after, the American Rheumatism-Association Medical-Information System (ARAMIS) was released.⁸ In this time-oriented record, all findings, histories, and medical data are displayed as a flow sheet. Much of the data was collected on encounter forms, while assessments were recorded as free text. The primary purpose of the system is to serve as a national research bank for the storage and disclosure of longitudinal data of rheumatic diseases. ARAMIS data was used to help determine diagnostic criteria, economic implications, and long-term

outcomes of disease and therapies. Less is known about its usefulness for care of the individual patient.

Other major systems such as the Regenrief Medical Record System (RMRS), developed by Clement J. McDonald at Wishard Memorial Hospital in Indianapolis, the Summary Time-Oriented Record (STOR, University of California, San Francisco), HELP (Latter-Day Saints Hospital, Salt Lake City), and The Medical Record (Duke University) were released in the 1970s and 1980s.⁶ These systems verified that electronic systems could improve clinical performance and patient care. The RMRS gave users warning messages of actions that should or should not be performed (preventive measures, contra-indicated drugs, etc.). The STOR system has been evaluated extensively, including a study that determined that a physician's predictive powers were better when the computer system was used than when using a paper medical record.⁶

However, medicine did not immediately embrace the EPR. Several of the earlier systems were not and still are not paperless, meaning clinicians used both an electronic and written chart in clinics. Our culture was not very computer-literate when these electronic forums were first developed, and users complained that data entry took too long. Some clinics hired clerks to enter data from structured forms physicians completed during patient visits. These issues were reflective of organizational transitions as well as development of the computer media that support EPR implementation. In 1991, an Institute of Medicine report concluded that no current system was capable of supporting the complete computerized medical record because of both technological and non-technological barriers.⁹

Since the IOM report, medicine has advanced in its quest to adopt the EPR. Several specialty records, such as those for patients with HIV infection, are used in multiple institutions to manage patients undergoing treatment.¹⁰ This allows clinics to pool data for clinical research because all health care providers use the same assessment tools to gauge patient disease and outcomes of treatment. This is a tremendous benefit, particularly for the study of rare diseases.

At present, several dental schools in North America are implementing portions of electronic systems, and many others have plans to buy or develop electronic systems in the near future. Many use a hybrid paper/electronic system or have individual clinics using packages designed for individual practitioners. The needs of educational institutions

are far more complex than those of private practices. This paper summarizes features of dental EPRs currently available for purchase with particular attention to the unique functions essential to dental schools and areas that need further development.

Evaluating EPRs for Dentistry

The authors evaluated electronic patient records (EPRs) for dentistry using criteria extracted from two documents produced by the American Dental Association (ADA), which is an American National Standards Institute (ANSI)-accredited organization. The ADA Standards Committee for Dental Informatics (SCDI) produced “ANSI/ADA Specification No. 1000 for Standard Clinical Data Architecture for the Structure and Content of an Electronic Health Record.” The SCDI predecessor, the ADA ANSI Accredited Standards Committee MD 156 Task Group on Dental Informatics, published “ADA Technical Report No. 1004: Computer Software Performance for Dental Practice Software.” Both publications were developed by volunteer working groups of experts in dental informatics. Both are available at www.ada.org/prof/prac/stands/index.html.^{11,12} The criteria in these documents were expanded after we reviewed the medical literature, which focused on the uses of EPRs for the management of clinical practice, indicators for use in the assurance of quality care, and the acquisition of clinical data for research (Table 1).

The commercial software products we evaluated were AxiUm (Exan Academic, Inc.), QSI (Quality Systems, Inc), Quick Recovery (General Systems Design, Inc.), Dentrax (Henry Schein Company), Softdent (DENTSPLY Infsoft), Dental.com (Thompson Dental Company), and Eaglesoft (Patterson Company). This paper reports the findings and suggestions of our internal review committee that assessed the capabilities of available EPR systems for our school. This committee included three members of the Department of Information Technology department (all with degrees in computer science or engineering), the Assistant Director of Dental Informatics for the Veterans’ Administration, a dentist with an advanced degree in Information Technology, and two dentists with extensive experience in clinical research and database management.

The primary concerns of most available software systems are procedure treatment planning, documentation of completed procedures, financial trans-

actions, and scheduling. Most systems lack scalability—that is, there is no enterprise version capable of supporting an entire dental school. Generally, systems were deficient in one or more of the following areas: security and privacy in a dental school environment, medical and dental history, a coding system for dental diagnoses, examination results, radiographic interpretation, treatment planning, education and quality assurance, and research.

Security and Privacy Issues

Dental school clinics require two signatures (co-signatures) for most entries: the student provider and the attending licensed faculty member. Both signatures are necessary to meet state legal requirements as well as accreditation guidelines. This co-signature security feature is not available in EPRs developed for private practice environments, though at least one developer is adding this feature to its enterprise version. Other security and privacy issues raised by new HIPAA regulations involve access to electronic patient records. While faculty may need to retrieve the record of any patient, students rarely need records other than those of the patients that they treat. The ideal EPR for a dental school clinic would have an option to limit the read access privileges of individual users.

Other basic security requirements include password protection or biometric controls for patient data viewing, a complete audit trail that identifies all modifications with date and name, and the inclusion of the date and name on all chart entries. The login system should be quick for faculty who simply need to approve chart entries and enter grades. Another essential security requirement is an automatic shutdown feature during long periods of inactivity to prevent record viewing by unauthorized users.

Many commercial systems have adequate audit trails for the EPR, but do not have the ability to document changes to digital images. This authority often remains within the software package of the digital system used in conjunction with the EPR. Integration and compatibility of software and hardware from different vendors are critical to the success of an enterprise approach.

Medical and Dental History

Most EPRs contain questions that capture the patient’s past and current medical and dental history.

Table 1. Criteria used to evaluate electronic patient record software. Criteria from ADA Technical Report 1004 are indicated by TR1004. All others are those from University of Maryland Dental School after considering our unique clinic environment.

Basic Requirements

Patient ID and assignment
 Unlimited number of patients
 Unlimited number of providers
 Unique patient identifier
 Assignment of patient to multiple providers or clinics
 Establishes patient relationship to different organizations (grants and contracts)
 Patient look up by name, I.D. number, or parts thereof (TR1004)
 Patient linked to family members (TR1004)

Security Issues

Password-protected for patient data viewing (TR1004)
 Electronic student signature for all entries
 Electronic faculty countersignature mandatory for all student entries
 Access limited at multiple levels
 Students only have access to assigned patient records
 Audit trail for all fields (TR1004)
 All chart entries date stamped
 Audit trail for modifications with date and name
 All chart entries locked once made

Patient History

Supports medical history interview and recording (TR1004)
 Medical history can be modified to fit institution (can maintain, update, add)
 Ability to capture medical history with standardized coding
 Records current smoking status (yes/no)
 Records smoking pack-year history
 Records alcohol use (yes/no)
 Records amount of alcohol use
 Medical health alerts are displayed (TR1004)

Clinical Data

Method for recording

- Caries
- Restorations with material
- Periodontal findings
- Soft tissue pathology
- Hard tissue pathology (other than teeth)
- Radiographic pathology

Ability to Record

- Anatomic site and, if written, associations must be clear
- Subjective symptoms (pain) recorded, possibly using standardized, validated scales
- TMD evaluation
- Occlusal evaluation
- Diagnostic tests (pulp testing, percussion, etc.)
- Each dental specialty will have the ability to customize sections for their departments to capture other information unique to their programs.

Diagnostic Processes

Differential diagnoses recorded
 Record indicates biopsy is recommended
 Record indicates biopsy was taken and report is needed (generates list for QA purposes)
 Final diagnosis
 Prognosis
 Pathology reports stored in record with appropriate ICD-9 code

Compares data in the periodontal module (e.g., attachment levels over a two-year period, TR1004)
 Calculates DMFT and DMFS from odontogram
 Ability to search portions of the EPR using key-search words

Treatment-Planning Module

Students can prepare and store draft treatment plans
 Onscreen planning—virtual charting
 Multiple treatment plans can be generated and stored until faculty and patient approval (TR1004)
 Multiple approval levels for treatment plans (perio, restorative, etc.)
 Treatment plan approval by patient is required for acceptance
 Treatment plan broken down by visit with financial requirements, time spreads, and any notes presented on a report to give to the patient (TR1004)
 Can retain deleted and/or changed treatment plan items, and identify them as deleted and/or changed (TR1004)
 Can utilize a “status” to be applied to any treatment plan and any changed item (TR1004)
 Explanatory notes can be stored in association with individual treatment plan items (TR1004)
 Treatment plans can be constructed in phases (TR1004)
 Treatment plans can be sorted and reordered as needed, with an audit trail of each transaction (TR1004)
 Printed treatment plans indicate date/time and user printing the treatment plan (TR1004)
 Can transmit treatment plans electronically to third-party carriers for pre-determinations (TR1004)
 Can automatically calculate insurance benefits and patient financial liability when entering procedures on a treatment plan (TR1004)
 Treatment plans can be stored and billed out to the insurance company as work is actually completed (TR1004)
 Treatment acceptance vs planned treatment plan correlates with estimate of insurance benefits (TR1004)
 Can print incomplete treatment plans by (TR1004):
 provider
 procedure
 user-defined criteria
 Specific procedures can be linked to dental or medical diagnostic codes

Procedures Tracking

Tracking of procedures performed (TR1004)
 Tracking of procedures by different providers (TR1004)
 Tracking of procedures pending (TR1004)
 Comprehensive display of treatment completed and planned (TR1004)
 Recording of all ADA-approved treatment and diagnostic codes (TR1004)
 Recording of associated modifiers to ADA codes particular to specialties (TR1004)
 Student and faculty identified for all student procedures
 Student signatures must be countersigned before procedure is accepted
 Entry of a completed procedure generates a grade

Progress Notes

Text notes entered as mixture of templates and free text
 Templates (drop down menus) can be customized by the institution to capture data for future analysis

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Table 1. Criteria used to evaluate electronic patient record software, cont.

Custom macros can be generated and stored to facilitate entry after common procedures (extractions, alloys)
Progress notes must be linked to date, procedures, providers, and clinics to enable sorting and display

Radiology

Accepts scanned traditional radiographic film images
Digital radiology interface
Section for radiology assessment
Altered image storage with time/date stamp and indication it is an altered image (TR1004)

Prescription

Prescription writer (electronic and/or printed, TR1004)
Can generate prescription history by drug and provider
Prescription posted to progress note

Other Features

Post-operative instructions and other customized instructions for patients can be generated, stored, and printed as needed
Consent to treatment forms can be stored and printed as needed
Signed consent form can be scanned and stored in record
Other clinic documents can be scanned in and stored as a PDF file
Form letters and medical consults can be generated and stored

Additional Links and Issues

Data can be exported
Data can be extracted easily without significant cost
Links to other resources (NLM, PDR, Harrison's)
Scheduled appointment generates CMS order

Each school should have the ability to easily modify the medical and dental histories to reflect the school's patient population and to add new questions when necessary (such as the use of fenfluramine and phentermine, commonly known as Fen-phen) without additional programming costs.

Medical and dental histories should be recorded in dental EPRs with standardized medical coding and classification systems. This additional coding will be advantageous in the future as electronic medical records become more uniform. In the future, dental schools should be able to download and store more complete and accurate medical information from medical electronic sources. This will require that dental schools use the same coding schemes as medicine. Medical information of patients treated within a university health complex that have both medical and dental clinics can be transferred easily between clinics if uniform coding is used to capture the medical history and the information is stored in database fields. Soon patients may carry a wallet-sized medical smart card, embedded with a programmable computer chip, that stores the patient's clinical and insurance information. Medical records will be updated on the card at every patient visit.¹³ Similarly, the patient's record may reside on the Internet and be accessed via a browser.

Significant active medical problems and current medications should be highlighted and appear throughout the electronic records in a form that is easily retrieved. A small box listing this information could appear throughout the record, such as at the beginning of specialty modules.

Patient Complaints, Problem Lists, and Diagnoses

Ideally, a patient's problems should be recorded in standardized manner. Standardized coding and classifications form the basis of structured text in many electronic records. Several systems can capture both symptoms and disease in medicine; these include International Classification of Diseases, 9th revision, Clinical Modification (ICD-9), SNOMED International, North American Nursing Diagnosis Association Taxonomy 1, Omaha System, Home Health Care Classification, and Nursing Outcomes Classification. All assess function and symptom status, and Nursing Outcomes also assesses quality of life.

SNOMED International is a system of terms with associated codes that classify a broad range of variables related to a patient's symptom and functional status. It is the most widely accepted standardized coding and classification system in the world and has developed a formal relationship with dentistry. SNODENT, developed by the American Dental Association to complement and enhance SNOMED, has not been released for use by the ADA as of this date. SNODENT will use SNOMED terms covering diagnoses, signs, symptoms, and complaints related to oral health problems. The SNODENT system could be used to record dental diagnoses, clinical outcomes, and document co-morbidity in a manner consistent with other healthcare specialties. More information about SNOMED is available at www.snomed.org/.

No software system currently available contains a consensus-standardized nomenclature for dental diagnoses and treatment outcomes, since no consensus dental classification system is available for software developers. The most widely used coding system, ICD-9, has limited coding for dentistry and was found to be inadequate in capturing the dental diagnoses of children seen at the emergency room with a dental complaint.¹⁴

Examination Results

All EPRs should record standard clinical findings, such as missing teeth, caries, existing restorations (with the type of material) and other previous treatment, periodontal findings, and soft and hard tissue pathology. The anatomic site must be noted, preferably by template or with graphics. Other pertinent diagnostic data, such as occlusal analysis and temporomandibular joint examination, should be captured, possibly with templates.

Several commercial systems only partially record the current oral health status of patients. Dental charting modules frequently just show current and planned restorations with no method for indicating caries, fractured teeth, or defective restorations. Existing restorations and active caries are not charted for those teeth needing immediate treatment. In several software packages, it is impossible to determine why, for example, an onlay was prescribed for a particular tooth. Periodontal data comparisons (such as demonstrating changes in attachment level over two years) are incorporated into several commercial packages, and some offer templates to indicate the color and texture of periodontal tissues. In general, these systems are oriented toward treatment procedures planned and lack a method of coupling diagnoses to specific treatments.

In most packages, there is little or no place to record mucosal pathology except as a note, either in the progress notes or examination area. In an educational setting, it would be more desirable to have this data recorded through forced choice templates that indicate lesion type, location, and size. This not only enhances the accuracy of the entry, but also enables recording the information as database elements, which will allow the extraction of the data for future studies. Data stored as free text in an area such as "notes" is very difficult to recover in a meaningful manner when conducting later searches of the database. The fact that the data is stored as data elements rather than as text

should be transparent to the user entering the information. Areas of the record describing tissues submitted for pathological examination should contain the ICD-9 code for the clinical diagnosis. The subsequent pathology report with the final diagnostic ICD-9 code should be linked to the portion of the record containing the clinical note. Acquisition of visible light patient images offers an additional dimension for documenting clinical findings.

Radiographic Pathology

The majority of systems reviewed do not provide a separate area for interpretation of radiographs. The user is expected to enter this data in the software of a digital radiology program. This is problematic, as a user may need to toggle back and forth between two software packages to view comments made about images by the Oral and Maxillofacial Radiology faculty. In many packages, it is not clear where comments belong about images produced on standard radiographic film at schools that do not yet have digital radiology.

Altered images stored with time/date stamp with a note that an image was altered must be included in any digital radiology software package. The images should be stored in a Digital Image and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) format to facilitate retrieval and sharing of images both today and in the future.

Treatment Planning

Many functions in a typical dental school clinic revolve around the treatment plan. First, treatment planning is a clinical discipline that students must master for clinical competency. Often, more than one clinical specialty must approve the final treatment plan, which requires that the software package not accept the treatment plan without all necessary approvals. In general, EPRs support procedure-based treatment planning functions except for the treatment plan approval procedure. Treatment procedure sequencing and scheduling linkages are missing in some of the EPR systems reviewed. Available EPRs are oriented toward planned procedures, ledgers for billing, and preparation of third-party claims.

Most commercial software can display treatment that has been completed, is in progress, and is planned. This is essential for clinics in which multiple providers care for an individual patient. Soft-

ware functioning in a large clinic must be able to bill and credit payments for individual transactions to the department or provider of the treatment. The software should create and track referrals between clinic and/or departments. Patients should be able to receive an updated report reflecting remaining out-of-pocket expenses, expected insurance payments, and estimated time for completion. Clinical software must have the ability to display the treatment by provider and date, and treatment should be converted to ADA-approved treatment codes with necessary descriptors such as tooth number, surfaces, and quadrant. Instructors also need to view the original treatment plan as well as the deleted or changed procedures. Patients must accept and sign the treatment plan to ensure that they accept the treatment and all associated costs. Accepted treatment plans should be able to be printed or transmitted electronically to insurance companies for pre-authorization when required. Exceptional packages update clinical charting automatically as planned procedures are completed.

The software should also ask for and store clinic grades when necessary. Most dental schools teach students to construct a treatment plan in phases, so EPR software must support this function. Various decision-tree structures and other “intelligent” functions would be highly desirable, as would the capability to enter some user-defined database elements for customization at a particular school.

Progress Notes

Progress notes are usually entered as a free-form narrative in a written record. Entering the note as free text in an EPR minimizes the advantages of an electronic database. Minimally, the date, clinic, providers, procedure (CDT3) codes with necessary descriptors such as tooth number, surfaces, and quadrant diagnostic (ICD9) codes should be required for every entry, linked to other data elements stored for the patient, and stored as data elements in addition to storage as a text progress note. This allows the future display of the notes by a variety of data sorts, such as chronology, provider, problem, tooth number, or specialty clinic. For example, all treatment notes related to tooth #14 can be displayed together. Several authors feel a mixture of free text and templates is the best structure for the progress notes of electronic records.¹⁵ The addition of templates, wizards, or reminders to electronic patient records results in more consistent documentation and increased compliance.^{4,6}

Many electronic record applications use structured texts, such as the following standard operative note that requires the student enter missing fields: “The preparation included the ____ surfaces of tooth # ____ . After placing _____ (type in type of base or choose from a pull-down menu) as a base, the tooth was restored with _____ (fill in material or choose from a pull-down menu). _____ ml of _____ (type in anesthetic or choose from a pull-down menu) was used for anesthesia.” The note displaying the text and choices would be posted to the EPR progress note section as text.

Data chosen from a list of stored choices is very easy to extract from the progress notes if the EPR uses a modern database. In the example above, the type of base and restorative material could be retrieved for future use. Another method to structure a progress note is with a series of templates. Users make a choice for every field before the note is accepted. A surgical post-operative note might require clinicians to quantify pain using a validated scale, swelling, temperature, bleeding, and other adverse events. Clinicians using these formats are more likely to report adverse events. In addition, progress notes need space to enter free text notes as needed. Some commercial systems allow users to create and store structured notes, but the use of forced-choice templates in the progress notes section is not a standard feature of most software packages.

Educational Issues

Dental educators teach patient evaluation through the clinical record. The emergency clinic evaluation form used by the University of Maryland Dental School is an illustration of this teaching technique. The student must complete the following for each emergency patient: chief complaint, history of present illness, present and past significant medical history, examination (including diagnostic testing such as percussion sensitivity), radiographic findings, differential diagnosis, working diagnosis, treatment plan, treatment rendered, and disposition. This traditional standardized method of initial patient evaluation, universally taught in medical and dental schools, has not been incorporated into any EPR reviewed by the authors. In fact, many records encourage students to truncate the evaluation and diagnostic processes that dental educators teach. Some EPRs encourage clinicians to determine the final treatment for patients while charting. Most EPRs do not systemati-

cally support data collection beyond the charting of teeth and periodontal status. Ideally, the EPR should allow individual schools to customize data collection sections to support their educational mission.

Research

Many schools hope to use the EPR for clinical research, but more work is needed to enhance current EPRs for this purpose. Some EPRs have a database that is not easily accessed. Realistically, only data entered into tables or through templates can be retrieved as database elements. Outcomes entered as free text in a clinic or progress note are very difficult to access through a search or to use for outcomes studies.

At present, patient demographic data, medical history data, and planned/completed procedures can be extracted from some EPRs running in a Windows environment. However, this will not indicate why a procedure was prescribed, as the current method of recording dental therapy does not include attaching a diagnosis to treatment. Dentistry typically does not indicate systematically why an extraction, for example, was indicated for a tooth. The reason may be buried in the progress note (caries, fractured tooth, etc.), but that data is not readily available for retrospective analyses.

To enhance the research potential of the EPR, modules should be included that can be customized for longitudinal data collection. These types of forms could be used to follow dental restorations, implants, prosthetic devices, or any other outcome across time. Student clinicians, residents, or faculty would be required to make the same pre-defined clinical judgments (such as mobility of an implant using an accepted scale) every time the patient is seen. The various clinical departments should develop some hypotheses that they hope to answer with the EPR and then design a method to acquire and retrieve the needed data elements electronically. Any EPR must be flexible enough to support collection of research data without additional source code programming.

Faculty hoping to use the EPR for future research should bear in mind that the best method for collecting data is prospectively. Defined criteria for assessing outcomes, defined frequencies of evaluation, and appropriate control subjects should be established before gathering data. Clinicians trying to use the EPR for retrospective analyses without proper planning will face many frustrations. Patients typically are not seen at regular intervals, clinicians evalu-

ate the dentition and oral health using different methods, and resulting data extracted from the group is invariably incomplete.

Quality Assurance

The EPR can be used to assess the quality of care in a large clinic in numerous ways.¹⁵ Any electronic dental record should be flexible enough to allow the comparative analysis of patients and by individual or groups of providers. The use of quality indicators will enable outcomes-based quality improvement, which is advocated by the Health Care Financing Administration (HCFA). For example, the EPR could be used to generate a report indicating missing biopsy reports and medical consults, patients still in active treatment that have not been seen in thirty, sixty, or ninety days, and overdue recalls. Required fields in the emergency care or oral examination modules ensure that users provide all necessary information before the entry is accepted for filing data.

A more sophisticated application of the electronic record is to capture patient perceptions of their problems, which are often inconsistent with those of providers. The EPR could also be used for collecting traditional patient satisfaction surveys while they wait for their appointments.

Data from the EPR must be exportable to other software packages for further analyses to support many quality assurance functions. Also, the EPR must be able to demand certain fields before the entry is accepted (such as a patient signature on a consent form), and block functions if certain procedures are not complete (such as payment for unauthorized treatment or appointments for unassigned patients).

Other Features

Large clinics often track the number and types of prescriptions written for their patients, and this task is simple if prescriptions are written via the EPR. Prescribing medications electronically ensures that a note containing all details of the prescription is posted in the patient's chart. Some EPR software will not accept a prescription if the individual's electronic health history indicates he or she is allergic to that medication.

Other desirable features of an EPR include a method for generating and storing consents, a sedation log, collection of medical history data, customizable post-operative instructions in multiple

languages that can be stored and printed at will, and customizable modules sections for different clinics, especially graduate clinics. Patient education for informed decision-making could also be a component of the EPR. The software should have easy links to other resources such as the National Library of Medicine, a software package containing information about pharmaceuticals, and other textbooks such as *Harrison's Internal Medicine*. Studies suggest that these types of resources are accessed more frequently if they are present at the clinic workstation rather than in the office.⁵ Other desirable features in dental EPRs include a provision for standardized patient letters, specialty consults or referrals, and links to other billing systems.

Vendor Issues

One of the biggest concerns of educational institutions with limited financial resources is vendor support, stability, and viability. The reader is strongly encouraged to read the list of questions for vendors in ADA Technical Report 1004: Computer Software Performance for Dental Practice Software.¹²

Conclusions

Many EPR packages are available for purchase, but at this time none meets all needs of a large dental school clinic. However, the expansion of clinical information systems to include all dental records is just beginning and should be pursued by dental academic facilities throughout the world.¹⁶ The first complete system in an institution should be simple and user-friendly (intuitive); if it is not, staff, students, and faculty will reject it. Also, the data must be in a form that can be exported easily to the next generation of software, as systems outdate quickly.

The dental profession should work together to define a more common record with standard diagnostic codes and clinical outcome measures to make the EPR more useful for clinical research. Incremental, modular, and iterative improvement will be necessary to develop a computer-based patient record that is viable in an environment of ever-changing software, hardware, and innovative clinical practices.

Acknowledgments

This project was supported by the University of Maryland Dental School, the ADEA Leadership Institute, and the Harald Løe Scholars Program.

REFERENCES

1. Tierney WM, Overhage JM, McDonald CJ. Demonstrating the effects of IAMIS on health care quality and cost. *J Am Med Inform Assoc* 1997;4(Suppl):S41-5.
2. Retchin SM, Wenzel RP. Electronic medical record systems at academic health centers: advantages and implementation issues. *Acad Med* 1999;74:493-8.
3. Morgan MM, Goodson J, Barnett GO. Long-term changes in compliance with clinical guidelines through computer-based reminders. *Proc AMIA Symp* 1998;493-7.
4. Schriger DL, Baraff LJ, Buller K, Shendrikar MA, Nagda S, Lin EJ, et al. Implementation of clinical guidelines via computer charting system: effect on the care of febrile children less than three years of age. *J Am Med Inform Assoc* 2000;7:186-95.
5. Shiffman RN, Liaw Y, Brandt CA, Corb GJ. Computer-based guideline implementation systems: a systemic review of functionality and effectiveness. *J Am Med Inform Assoc* 1999;6:104-14.
6. Tange HJ, Hasman A, de Vries Robbe PF, Schouten HC. Medical narratives in electronic medical records. *Int J Med Inf* 1997;46:7-29.
7. Weed LL. Medical records that guide and teach. *N Engl J Med* 1968;278:593-600,652-7.
8. Fries JF, McShane DJ. ARAMIS (the American Rheumatism Association Medical Information System): a prototypical national chronic-disease data bank. *West J Med* 1986;145:798-804.
9. Dick RS, Stein EB. *The computer-based patient record: an essential technology for health care*. Washington, DC: National Academy Press, 1991.
10. Smith D. The HIV epidemiology research study, HIV outpatient study, and the spectrum of disease studies. *J Acquir Immune Defic Syndr* 1998;17(suppl 1):S17-19.
11. ADA Standards Committee on Dental Informatics. ANSI/ADA Specification No. 1000 for standard clinical data architecture for the structure and content of an electronic health record. Chicago: American Dental Association, 2000.
12. ADA Accredited Standards Committee MD 156 Task Group on Dental Informatics. ADA Technical Report No. 1004: computer software performance for dental practice software. Chicago: American Dental Association, 1998.
13. Krohn RW. Medical smart cards: health care access in your pocket. *Med Group Manage J* 2000;Suppl:22-3,26-7.
14. Ettlbrick KL, Webb MD, Seale NS. Hospital charges for dental caries related emergency admissions. *Pediatr Dent* 2000;22:21-5.
15. Henry SB, Morris JA, Holzemer WL. Using structured text and templates to capture health status outcomes in the electronic health record. *Joint Commission Journal on Quality Improvement* 1997;23:667-77.
16. Schleyer T, Spallek H. Dental informatics: a cornerstone of dental practice. *J Am Dent Assoc* 2001;132:605-13.